

figure the stepwise stability constants will be as given below ;

Complex	Log K_1	log K_2	log K_3	log K_4
$\text{Cu}(\text{HMBMA})_4\text{SO}_4$	8.22	2.56	2.30	2.70
			log $\beta_4 = 15.78$	

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Nickel (II) Complexes of some new Tridentate (ONN) Dibasic Schiff Bases

NITYANANDA SAHA and B. N. MALICK

Department of Pure Chemistry, University College of Science, Calcutta-700009

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ALTHOUGH transition metal complexes of salicyldehyde schiff bases have been extensively studied^{1,2}, very little work has been reported³ particularly on the coordination behaviour of ONN

donor tridentate schiff bases (derived from salicyldehyde). This preliminary communication reports syntheses and characterisation of several nickel(II) complexes with four new schiff bases derived from salicyldehyde or 5-substituted salicyldehyde and nitroaminoguanidine.

Experimental

(A) Syntheses of schiff bases :

All the four schiff bases were prepared by refluxing a mixture of aqueous alcoholic solutions of nitroaminoguanidine (0.01 mole) and R-salicyldehyde (0.01 mole) (R=H, 5-Cl, 5-Br and 5-NO₂) for one hour. The schiff bases (R-SBH₂) having light yellow colour with varying shades, are insoluble in water but soluble in aqueous alcohol (R=5-Cl, 5-Br) or in alkaline alcoholic solution (R=H, 5-NO₂) Anal : R-SBH₂ :

- R=H m.p. 220° (d), (Found : N, 31.80 ; C, 42.84 ; H, 3.82. Calcd for C₈H₉O₈N₂ : N, 31.45 ; C, 43.05 ; H, 4.03%)
- R=5-Cl m.p. 225° (d), (Found : N, 27.52 ; C, 37.42 ; H, 2.90. Calcd for C₈H₈O₈N₂Cl : N, 27.18 ; C, 37.28 ; H, 3.10%)
- R=5-Br m.p. 227° (d), (Found : N, 22.98 ; C, 31.52 ; H, 2.44. Calcd for C₈H₈O₈N₂Br : N, 23.18 ; C, 31.79 ; H, 2.65%)
- R=5-NO₂ m.p. 252° (d), (Found : N, 31.68 ; C, 35.60 ; H, 2.72. Calcd for C₈H₈O₈N₄ : N, 31.34 ; C, 35.83 ; H, 2.98%)

(B) General method for the syntheses of the complexes :

- [NiR-SB H₂O]_n H₂O (R=H, 5-Cl, 5-Br, 5-NO₂)

On mixing either an alcoholic solution (R=5-Cl, 5-Br) or an alkaline alcoholic solution (R=H, 5-NO₂) of the schiff base (0.01 mole) with an aqueous alcoholic solution of NiCl₂ · 6H₂O (0.01 mole), a deep red solution resulted, when the pH of the solution was adjusted to 6~7 by addition of dil NaOH or ammonia solution whenever necessary. The resulting solution was refluxed for one hour and the orange-red compound, in each case, was collected on the filter, washed with ethanol and dried in a desiccator over silica gel.

- [NiR-SBX]_nH₂O (X=py, β-picoline and γ-picoline)

These mixed ligand complexes were prepared either by reaction of the corresponding aquo-variety (suspended in alcohol) with the respective base and subsequent evaporation of the resulting solution on water bath or by refluxing a mixture of schiff base (0.01 mole), NiCl₂ · 6H₂O (0.01 mole) and the corresponding base (0.01 mole) in aqueous alcoholic or alkaline ethanolic solution. In each case, an orange-yellow compound was collected, dried as before by washing with alcohol and acetone.

Results and Discussion

The schiff bases, R-SBX₂, having given the structural formulation I from elemental analyses, are also recognised from i.r. spectra which exhibit most characteristic bands in the 3 μ region (3400 and 3200 cm⁻¹), at 1600 cm⁻¹ and also at 1260 cm⁻¹ attributable to -NH, C=N and C-O stretching vibrations respectively^{4,5}.

All the nickel (II) complexes [NiR-SBX]_nH₂O, (X=H₂O, py, β and γ -pic) show in their i.r. spectra, a single broad band at 3380 cm⁻¹ indicating involvement of the nitroganyl group (with deprotonation) in complexation⁶; moreover, lowering of -C=N and increase of C-O stretching frequencies in the complexes as compared to the free ligand point to the participation of the azomethine and phenolic -OH group in bonding with the metal^{6,7}.

All the present orange-red Ni (II) complexes are diamagnetic as ascertained from magnetic

susceptibility measurements (Gouy method using G.R. CuSO₄, 5H₂O as calibrant). The mull spectra (recorded in liquid paraffin in a Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer) of the complexes show a principle absorption band between 22,500-24,500 cm⁻¹ (Table I) which may be attributed to ¹B₁ ← ¹A₁ transition⁸ in a square-planar geometry. The insolubility of the complexes in water and innocent organic solvents and in some cases in donor solvents suggest strong association between the planar molecules in the solid state. In a few cases the solution of the complexes in a donor solvent like pyridine does not show any spectral change and this lack of solvation or coordination (by a solvent) may be ascribed to the strong ligand field favoring square planar configuration.

Detailed studies of the coordination behaviour of these and other schiff base ligands derived from nitroaminoguanidine with metal ions are in progress.

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TABLE—1 ANALYTICAL AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF [NiR-SBX]_nH₂O

R	X	n	% of Ni		% of N		Electronic spectra (mull) λ_{max} (cm ⁻¹)
			Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	
H	H ₂ O	3	16.45	16.64	19.95	19.90	23,500 ; 15,630 (sh)
"	Py	2	14.97	14.87	20.75	21.27	23,260 ; 16,400 (sh)
"	β -pico	2	15.92	14.36	17.96	17.12	23,260 ; 16,130 (sh)
"	γ -pico	2	14.30	14.36	17.15	17.12	23,530 ; 14,810 (sh) 11,910 (s b)
5-Cl	H ₂ O	1	17.02	16.76	19.43	19.99	23,530 ; 15,380 (sh)
"	Py	1	13.76	14.28	21.02	20.43	22,730
"	β -pico	0	14.86	14.41	20.42	20.63	23,260 ; 15,630 (sh)
"	γ -pico	1	13.73	13.80	20.22	19.75	23,260
5-Br	H ₂ O	1	14.72	14.87	18.20	17.73	24,390 ; 15,630 (sh)
"	Py	1	12.79	12.88	18.31	18.44	23,500
"	β -pico	1	12.32	12.49	17.69	17.88	24,000
"	γ -pico	0	12.79	12.99	18.92	18.60	23,820 ; 15,630 (sh)
5-NO ₂	H ₂ O	1	16.53	16.28	23.04	23.29	24,390
"	Py	0	15.06	14.88	23.81	24.28	23,580
"	β -pico	0	15.20	14.06	23.14	23.46	22,600
"	γ -pico	0	14.17	14.06	23.09	23.46	23,500

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